

ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS IN CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS LIVING IN THE ARALE ZONE

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The incidence of congenital heart defects is 0.8% of live births. 10 years ago, almost every three-year-old child died from this pathology and every fifth did not live to reach the age of one. But today, thanks to the intensive development of cardiac surgery. It has become possible to provide effective medical care for almost all types of congenital heart disease in children even in the neonatal period. Thanks to which the life expectancy of children with congenital heart disease has increased, which allows minimizing the severe consequences of the long-term existence of congenital heart disease. The only method of treating sick children with congenital heart disease is considered to be surgical correction of the defect, but unfortunately not all patients can do this while having sufficient financial support. One indication for early correction of congenital heart disease is considered to be suitable weight of children with a minimum of 7-8 kg. According to numerous data, all children with congenital heart disease have underweight and impaired anthropometric indicators, which is considered a contraindication to surgical correction of the defect.

Purpose of the study: determining anthropometric profiles and prevalence of malnutrition in children with congenital heart disease using anthropometric measurements.

Results and discussions. A retrospective study of children aged 0-2 years with congenital heart disease was conducted in the city clinic No. 1 in the city of Urgench. All patients underwent anthropometric assessment (weight, length, and head circumference) upon admission. Malnutrition, developmental delay/FTT, short stature and microcephaly were defined by WHO, weight-for-length, weight-for-age 2 points, length-for-age, head circumference-for-age z-score < -2SD, respectively. The total number of patients studied was 120 patients, of which 64 were children with white defects, and 56 with blue type. The prevalence of malnutrition in congenital heart disease was 61.7%, with 18% severe malnutrition. FTT was found in 75%, short stature in 55%, and microcephaly in 17% of patients. FTT was found to be higher in acyanotic (71%) compared to cyanotic lesions (29%). In children with the white type, weight impairment was greater than length impairment (79% versus 42%). In children with white types, the ratio of body weight to body length was disturbed in equal numbers (45% versus 46%). Sick children with malnutrition were given dietary counseling. Medication, transcatheter, or surgery were indicated in selected patients.

Conclusions: The prevalence of FTT was higher than malnutrition in children with CHD. FTT was found higher in acyanotic lesions. In acyanotic lesions, weight was affected more than length. In cyanotic lesions, weight and length were equally affected.